

Strategic Human Resources Management practice, “are we there yet”? The Incorporation of a Human Resources Strategy within a University’s Strategic Plan

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Abstract—This study examines the structural and systematic processes of the Human Resources Division at The University of the West Indies, St. Augustine, Trinidad and Tobago for evidence of incorporation of the University’s 2012- 2017 Strategic Plan. In conducting the study the structure of the Human Resources Management Division and its functions were carefully reviewed and measured against the strategic direction of the organisation. Findings indicate disconnect between these areas as there is apparent failure of the Human Resources Division to totally align its mandate with that of the organisation’s strategic direction. This action serves to threaten the viability of the organisation and its efficiency and effectiveness as an institution. The recommendations being put forward are for the realignment of the Human Resources Management Division and for its focus to mirror that of the organisation and the organisation’s goals and objectives. This may entail a restructuring of the Division.

Keywords—Commonwealth Caribbean, Realignment, Region, Strategic Plan.

I. INTRODUCTION

A strategy is a statement of the value and competitive differentiation provided by the organisation [1] and strategic planning is a tool for organizing the present on the basis of the projections of the desired future. While [2] states that a strategic plan is a road map to lead an organization from where it is now to where it would like to be in five or ten years [2].

A strategic plan must be flexible and practical and yet serve as a guide to implementing programs, evaluating how these programs are doing and making adjustments when necessary [2]. Hence the development of a plan requires probing, discussion and examination of the views of the leaders who are responsible for the plan’s preparation. However, more often than not, the development of the plan is less complicated than is the implementation [2].

Implementation, in essence, carefully diffuses a plan throughout an organisation. Every unit within the organization which is involved must then accept the plan, agree to its direction, and implement specifications [2]. According to reference [3], employees at companies that

encourage Human Resources Management (HRM) participation in strategic planning have a stronger understanding of their functions, because in order to effectively and efficiently implement a plan, all individuals involved in its implementation must function as a whole or the plan is destined to fail. A Strategic Plan needs to include a Mission Statement, Objectives, Goals and an Action or Implementation Plan [2]. It should be noted that strategy without change is idle hope and that change without strategy is random action [4].

II. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to analyse the strategic direction of the Human Resources Management Division at The University of the West Indies, St. Augustine in terms of its alignment with the organisation’s 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan and to suggest recommendations for realigning the department’s goals and objectives to mirror that of the Strategic Plan in cases where it differs. Therefore in order to ensure efficiency and effectiveness in the department’s activities in terms of alignment with the strategic direction of the organisation, recommendations for administrative and structural reviews may be made to the Human Resources Management Division at the campus.

The University of the West Indies (UWI) was initially established in 1948 as an external College of the University of London. It was made fully independent in 1962 and is the oldest, regional institution of higher learning in the Commonwealth Caribbean. Supported by fifteen countries, all current or former colonies of Great Britain, The UWI is committed to the development of the region through the training of its human resources, conducting research, delivering advisory services to governments as well as to the private sector and forging links with other institutions in the wider region and the rest of the world [5].

The University has expanded to four campuses that serve diverse communities across the Caribbean region. The campuses are Cave Hill (in Barbados), Mona (in Jamaica), St. Augustine (in Trinidad and Tobago) and the Open Campus (online classes), all of which deliver high-quality education, research and services to all 15 contributing countries that support the University, as well as the Turks & Caicos Islands

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[5]. Since its strategic direction is defined by how it balances its internal strengths and weaknesses with external opportunities and threats in an effort to maintain its competitive advantage, a strategically aligned Human Resources Management focus is vital to the existence of the University.

In an effort to ensure the success of its 2012 -2017 Strategic Plan, the University Strategic Workforce Planning teams has been meeting to develop two year Operational Plans that will link the University's 2012 – 2017 Strategy to its strategic vision by identifying objectives, initiatives and projects, performance indicators, timelines, responsibilities and resources needed to ensure that the Strategic Plan is properly implemented [6]. This action will assist the organisation in executing an effective Strategic Workforce Plan. The initiative is also being strengthened by the desire of the Strategic Planning team to avoid the pitfalls associated with the implementation of the 2007 – 2012 Strategic Plan since it is felt that the 2007 – 2012 Strategic Plan failed because the Strategic Planning team failed to monitor the development and implementation of Operational Plans on all four campuses [6] and it has been shown that strategic plans commonly fail because of poor implementations.

In the way forward the University planning team has paid critical attention to establishing a strong mechanism for evaluating the 2012- 2017 Strategic Plan's progress, to regularly measure outputs as well as outcomes, and obtain feedback from its stakeholders. This is complemented by leadership enrichment and employee engagement initiatives. Essential to its success is strong, committed leadership to model the way, while fostering an environment and culture where the staff, which are the key resource, feel understood, heard and empowered to share the organisation's vision and values.

III. HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Strategic Human Resource Management (SHRM) is rooted in manpower planning. It was the work of influential management gurus such as [7] and [8], affirming the importance of the effective management of people as a source of competitive advantage, that encouraged academics to develop frameworks emphasizing the strategic role of the HR function and attaching the prefix "strategic" to the term "human resource management". Strategic Human Resource Management is globally recognized as the process that brings about effective and efficient use of an organisation and its human resource as it links the Human Resource function with the strategic objective of the organisation in order to improve performance, [3], thereby producing a documented Human Resources Strategy (HRS). A HRS serves to show the acceptance and commitment of a Human Resources Management Department to its organisation's Strategic Plan.

"The Human Resources Strategy (HRS) is view as the outcome of the mission, vision and priorities of the HR function [9]". The HRS is a multidisciplinary document and

requires the combined effort of all Human Resource Management based managers in the organisation to produce [10]. It is important that an organisation's Human Resources Management (HRM) policies and practices fits in with its strategy, in its competitive environment and with the immediate business conditions that it faces (Beer et al., 1984). The concept of integrating the policy has three aspects:- the linking of Human Resources (HR) policies and practices with the strategic management process of the organisation; the internalization of the importance of HR on the part of Line Managers and the integration of the workforce into the organisation to foster commitment or an "identify of interest" with the strategic goals. This approach has been referred to as the "matching" model [3].

Human Resources Strategy is designed to develop the skills, attitudes and behaviors among staff that will help the organization meet its goals. It consists of principles for managing the workforce through HR policies and practices and covers the various areas of human resources functions such as recruitment, compensation, performance management, reward and recognition, employee relations and training. Reference [11] framework suggests that those responsible for developing effective HR Strategies, and linking them to business strategies, have to adopt a conceptual and reflective approach to the task. This is so because determining an appropriate HRS in an organization is not simply about applying set techniques or simplified rules to the process, since there are no generally agreed tools of analysis or "magic bullets" for action in this area of HR management [12], instead it is a designed plan of action for the HR Department base on the organization's goals and objectives. A human resources strategy can be extremely valuable to a company, but only if it is successful [13]. It should be noted that specific human resources strategies will have different measures that are important, depending on the goal of the strategy (Clark, 2004).

Companies sometimes have difficulties measuring the effectiveness of a human resource strategy. To rectify this, an organization can use a balanced scorecard measurement approach to determine the achievement of strategic human resources goals (Colbert, 2002). The Balanced Scorecard allows the company to select the categories for measurement and then associate goals to those categories. This approach provides a more balanced assessment of the efficacy of the human resources department and the entire organization. Managers also play a role in measuring human resource strategy through providing necessary feedback on systems and program implementations.

Despite its benefits some managers and middle managers might not implement HR Strategies in the ways desired by senior colleagues because of:

- Lack of identification with employer goals
- Problems of work overload
- Limited investment in training and development
- The value of retaining some flexibility at workplace level

- Failure to apply organizational rules

It is therefore important that Human Resources Departments assist in ensuring that potential barriers to the success of the HRS are identified and eliminated.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In conducting the study the structure of the Human Resources Division its functions, concepts, policies, principles, systems, processes, procedures and job descriptions was carefully reviewed and measured against The University of the West Indies 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan which outlines the strategic direction of the organisation. Information gathered in interviews along with documented information collected was used in the process.

The information/documents that were reviewed were matched against organisational strategies and best practices to determine their relevance and applicability to international standards as well as the organisation's goals and objectives.

A. Research Questions

The study sought to answer the following research questions:

- Is the University of the West Indies – St. Augustine Human Resources Management Division strategic in nature?
- Will the Strategic Plan of the University of the West Indies be negatively affected if the Human Resources Management Division – St. Augustine fails to strategically align itself with the organisation's strategic direction?
- Is the organisational culture negatively affecting the practice of positive Human Resources Management policies and principles?

V. ORGANISATION CULTURE

According to [14] "organisational culture is a set of shared mental assumptions that guides the interpretation and action in organisations by defining appropriate behaviour for various situations". While, [15] defines it as "the core values, beliefs and assumptions that are widely shared by member of an organisation". However, [16] sees it as "the collective programming of the mind that distinguishes the members of one organisation from others". In an effort to map organisational culture in the 1980's Hofstede along with 20 Research Fellows conducted a successful research project which resulted in the creation of a model. The model consists of six autonomous dimension variables and two semi-autonomous dimensions and states that once the culture of an organisation has been mapped, the mapping can indicate whether culture will enable or hinder realization of whatever objective management want to realize. The research also showed that organizational culture differs mainly at the level of practice and that they are more superficial and more easily

learned and unlearned than the values which form the core of national cultures [1].

VI. COMPETENCE

Competence or Competences may be defined as the ability to perform activities within an occupation to a prescribed standard with the focus on the outcome [12]. The theory of competence-based strategic management is an integrative strategy theory that incorporates economic, organizational and behavioural concerns in a framework that is dynamic, systemic, cognitive and holistic [18]. The theory defines competence as the ability to sustain the coordinated deployment of resources in ways that helps an organization achieve its goals (creating and distributing value to customers and stakeholders). Though simple, this definition embodies essential aspects of the "four cornerstones" of the theory of competence-based strategic management, which aspires to recognize and capture the dynamic, systemic, cognitive and holistic nature of organizational competences [19].

VII. ORGANISATION CHART

An organizational structure refers to the formal relationships among jobs in an organization [20], while an Organization Chart is a "snapshot" of the organisation at a particular point in time and shows the skeleton of the organization's structure in chart form [21].

The organisation chart does not provide details about actual communication patterns, degree of supervision, amount of power and authority, or specific duties and responsibilities, although it indicates the types of departments established, the title of each manager's job, and by means of connecting lines clarifies the chain of command and shows who is accountable to whom [20].

In designing an organization one need to choose a structure that is in keeping with the company's strategic goals and objectives. There are three (3) basic types of organization structures; bureaucratic, flat and boundary-less. Bureaucratic designs are becoming less common, flat structures are increasingly the norms; and boundary-less organizations characterized by alliances and joint ventures have started to evolve. The HR Division of the University of the West Indies – St. Augustine is design along the lines of a Bureaucratic structure and is in keeping with the organisations strategic direction.

VIII. HUMAN RESOURCES METRICS (HR METRICS)

Human Resources Metric provides a number of factors that can be measured to show how Human Resource contributes to the business [22]. As mentioned earlier Human Resource Management is now a key role in developing and implementing corporate strategy.

HR Metric also provides a measurement and the analytical and data based decision-making capability to influence business strategy with an attempt to make better decision and transform HR into strategic partners.

Due to the strategic nature of HR Metric, organisations have benefited considerable from the impact of HR based initiatives across the organisation; hence it is important that organisations link the Metric to the Business Strategy, thereby allowing them to go beyond just activity-based measurements, to focus on the achievement of business goal.

IX. DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study examined documentations outlining the policies, principles and functions along with the organisational chart received from the Human Resources Management Division. Minutes of papers produced during/ after the various meetings that were held in relation to the 2012 - 2017 Strategic Plan for the University of the West Indies were also closely examined. As stated earlier interviews were held with the then HR Director, and as a result the analysis will be contained to the documented literature mentioned above along with the interview notes made during the interviews held with the HR Director.

X. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The paper was limited by the inability to conduct observations and work study analysis of the work processes in the Division. The Limitation also extended to interviews as only one member of the HR Division was interviewed. While conducting the study it was discovered that a contractual agreement existed between a Consulting Firm and the University of the West Indies – St. Augustine, Human Resources Management Division. The Terms of Reference for the contract reads as follows: “FOR CONSULTANCY SERVICES FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE STRATEGIC HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PROJECT- THE UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST INDIES”. The findings of the Firm were not made available to the Researcher. These noted limitations could serve to compromise the finding as discussions and recommendations are limited to the information received which may not necessarily fully represent the existing situation.

XI. DATA AND DATA ANALYSIS

Over the years the University has been documenting five years Strategic Plans with the aim of enhancing the organisation's efficiency and effectiveness with their implementations. Unfortunately, the Human Resources Management Department of the University of the West Indies – St. Augustine did not document a Human Resource Strategy to complement the organisation's 2007- 2012 Strategic Plan.

Due to the strategic positioning of Human Resources Management (HRM) Departments in organisations, the failure of a HRM Department to align itself strategically with its organisation's goals and objectives (thru the documentation of a HRS, policies, procedures and practices and the enforcement of same) may be considered organisational suicide as it serves to threaten the viability as well as the efficiency and effectiveness of the institution, because of the critical role an

HR Department “plays” in the “life” of an organisation. The HRM Division – St. Augustine has stated that it is presently documenting a HRS to support the University's current 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan.

A. *The University of the West Indies (UWI) 2007 – 2012 Strategic Plan*

A review of the 2007 – 2012 Strategic Plan at the Strategic Planning Retreat in 2011 revealed that incremental level of progress was being made in some areas identified in the Strategic Plan. One such area is with the “greater linkage of programmes to regional human resources needs [23]. However, despite the progress made it was noted that challenges were still being experienced in some areas of Human Resources Management. Some of the existing problems identified were: leadership/Management Skills, Culture Change, Communication, The attraction and retention of key-staff members, Employee engagement/motivation, career paths direction and workloads assignment.

B. *The University of the West Indies (UWI) 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan*

The University of the West Indies 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan utilises the Balanced Scorecard (BSC) framework for linking the vision of The UWI to its strategic goals and associated objectives. This framework allows for the identification of different perspectives/dimensions of the UWI's operations, the establishment of casual relationships between the perspectives and the specification and articulation of goals and associated strategic objectives design to assist in achieving the University's vision.

The Strategic planning and management system is used to align business activities to the vision and strategy of the organisation, improve internal and external communications and monitor organisation performance against strategic goals. It involves, the identification of operating perspectives, linkage of the vision of the organisation to the specific perspectives, development of casual links between the perspectives, development of a framework that identifies objectives and initiatives matched to time lines and Key Performance Indicators (KPI) thereby establishing accountability for all perspectives and the development of an incentive framework for goal achievement (The University of the West Indies. 2012. “The University of the West Indies 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan). For purposes of this paper emphasis has been placed on Perspective 2 – Employee Engagement and Development (outlined in the 2012-2017 Strategic Plan), as it speaks directly to the functions of the HR Department and as a result should constitute the core principles on which the HR Strategy is based. It should however be noted that Perspective 3 – Internal Operational Processes also comes under the mandate of the HR Division but will not be emphasized in this paper because of the focus of the paper which is on the Strategic alignment of the HRM Division.

The 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan will be supplemented by biennial Operational Plans which will coincide with the

current financing arrangements of The UWI. The Operational Plans will contain university-wide, campus specific and cross-campus activities undertaken in faculties, departments, centres and units. Annual reviews of the Operational Plans (which will employ the use of a Balanced Scorecard framework in the monitoring and evaluation phase of the plan) will be undertaken, as critical assessment of performance will help The UWI maximise the return to those who invest in the University and to all whom The UWI serves (The University of the West Indies. 2001. "The University of the West Indies 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan").

The main challenges that were encountered during the implementation phase of the 2007-2012 Strategic Plan were due to: the absence of an operational plan; the lack of financial resources necessary to undertake several of the initiative; the absence of an adequate monitoring and evaluation framework (due in part to the absence of the operational plan); the lack of a proper information management system along with the absence of a very important document – a Human Resources Strategy (HRS).

It should be noted that the success of the 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan and its associated Operational Plans will depend on critical factors such as the effective management and creative leadership of all levels in The UWI, adequate human and financial resources, appropriate accountability mechanism, an adequate incentive system, widespread ongoing support of staff and other stakeholders, cross-campus collaboration and effective communication and information management (The University of the West Indies. 2001. "The University of the West Indies 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan") and the documentation of a Human Resources Strategy which is vital to the process as it serves to fuel the success of the organisation's strategic process.

Therefore in order to ensure a successful implementation of the 2012-2017 Strategic Plan it is critical that the Human Resources Management Division aligns its HR strategies with the Strategic Plan as the strength of an HR Department usually determines an organisation's level of effectiveness and efficiency which is tied to the organisation's growth and development.

C. The UWI Organisational Culture

Culture is an important organisational factor influencing strategic management of the HR function [24] - [26]. Reference [26] commented that the type of culture an organisation has, exerts a strong influence on both its organisational and HR strategies. Thus, it is logical to expect HR activities and practices to alter following a change in organisational culture. Reference [27] noted that organisational culture is in part managed through HRM practices such as selection, training, compensation and employee retention., while in his definition [28] described two types of cultures: control-based and commitment-based.

In trying to determine the culture present at the UWI, one needs to be mindful that the university is more complex than other universities because it is geographically diverse

(campuses are located in different Caribbean countries) and has to meet different national legislation, sub-cultures and needs. In addition to which, the University needs to balance the central authority (Vice Chancellor), with its local (Campus) authorities in administering and managing University Affairs, all of which will affect the culture of the institution [5]. Despite the attempt to have a strong united organisational culture perpetuating the three main campuses, each campus has developed a culture of its own, which is based on factors such as its surrounding, location, political influence and local practices etc.

During a brain storming exercise conducted by the University with Senior Executive in Trinidad and Tobago before the documentation of the 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan, the CEO of the Royal Bank of Trinidad and Tobago stated that "UWI needs to make tough decisions early in relation to the importance of staff, staff development and change management as well as communications and cultural nuances within the workplace". This statement alludes to the fact that indecisiveness may allow cultural practices that are not in alignment with the strategic direction of the organisation to develop and thrive.

The results of the recently concluded Employee Engagement Survey showed where one employee described the organisation culture on the St. Augustine Campus as "a very loose culture". Although somewhat un-abashed and crude some persons have agreed with the statement. However, a more formal definition might describe the culture as "An internal politically driven organisation that lacks accountability, ethical practices and respect"

D. Human Resource Management

The St. Augustine Human Resources Management Division is divided into two distinct areas: the Human Resource Appointment's Section (Appointment's Section) and the Human Resources Office. All administrative functions relating to the contracts of newly appointed Academic, Senior Administrative and Professional (ASAP) staff along with benefit processing for the same group are handled by the Appointment's Section. While the Human Resources Office handles the recruitment and selection activities for the Administrative, Technical and Service (ATS) staff along with the other HR related functions such as Industrial Relations, Training and Development, Performance Management, Human Resources Information System (HRIS) and Employee Relations for both categories of staff.

The HR Division presently boasts a staff compliment of approximately 35 persons, while the total number assign to the St. Augustine's campus is 2,429, making it a ratio of approximately 70 staff members per HR employee. Without the delineation of HR services between both areas, the ratio of 1 HR staff to 70 employees although not ideal might be somewhat acceptable but, when one considers the split in service areas and the low level HR skills set of the Division, the number becomes uncomfortable, because, it could negatively affect both the services offered to the University's

population and the Division's ability to assist in ensuring the success of the organisation's strategic direction and that of the Division's.

Despite the above, at its 2012 Staff Retreat members of the Division agreed to provide a work environment which emphasizes commitment, responsibility, respect and personal success. It was also stated (at the Staff Retreat) that the Division welcomes positive thoughts, ideas and solutions as it strives for excellence by encouraging critical thinkers in its move forward towards the achievement of its goals and priorities [23].

E. Mission Statement- HR Division St. Augustine Campus

During the 2012 Staff Retreat the HRM Division documented its Mission Statement which reads as follows: "To recruit, develop and retain a cadre of highly motivated employees whose competencies fit the requirements of the job and who can effectively contribute to the accomplishment of the strategic objectives of the University of the West Indies" [23].

A slogan vowing commitment to the following principles was also documented at the Retreat: "To promote a work environment which emphasize commitment, responsibility, respect and personal success; To welcome positive thoughts, ideas and solutions as it strives for excellence; To encourage critical thinking as it moves forward with its goals and priorities which are aimed at achieving successful outcomes" [23].

F. Human Resources - St. Augustine Campus

Fig. 1 Human Resource Division Structure

As stated previously the Researcher was advised that the Human Resources Management Division of the University of the West Indies – St. Augustine is presently drafting its Human Resources Strategy. It was communicated to the Researcher that when completed the new document will highlight the alignment of the Division's goals and objectives with that of the University's 2012-2017 Strategic Plan and will address the following strategic perspectives (as outlined in the Strategic Plan document), namely: financial, employee

engagement and development, internal operational processes, teaching and learning, research and innovation and outreach.

The present organisational chart is drawn along functional lines and represents a vertical "organisational command", as it shows the HRIS, Employee Relations, Recruitment and Selection and the Organisation & Development Units all reporting directly to the Director of the Human Resources Management Division (Human Resources Management Division. 2009. "Organisational Chart").

Unlike the horizontal drawn organisational chart the vertical is usually used for organisations designed to capture efficiency, control, stability and reliability. While a functional organisational chart allows for economies of scale, enables the development of in-depth knowledge and skills and the ability of organisations to accomplish functional goals.

The Director of the Human Resources Management Division – St. Augustine has responsibility for all HR matters on the St. Augustine campus, however, the organisational chart shows the incumbent reporting to the Campus Registrar (whose responsibilities lies mainly with students' affairs) and not to the Campus Principal who's mandate includes staff matters. In addition to which the HR Director is omitted from the decision making body of the institution which comprise the Senior Membership team on the Campus, despite the fact that the responsibility of ensuring the success of the organisation's strategic plan, an extremely important aspect to the organisation's survival makes up the main part of HRM Director's portfolio.

The structural design of the present organisational chart for the HR Division appears to be suitable base on the direction of the strategic plan. However, there are concerns with the number of units and the functional responsibilities of each unit in addition to the reporting relationship of the HR Director (not shown on organisational chart). These concerns will be address in the Discussion and Recommendations sections of this report.

XII. FINDINGS

The findings indicate disconnect as the Human Resources Division – St. Augustine was not able to totally align its mandate with the organisation's strategic plan, and as a result was unable to adequately address the goals and objectives of the 2007 – 2012 Strategic Plan and may not be able to address those of the present Strategic Plan (2012 – 2017) for the same reason.

Areas of discrepancies are presently visible when one attempts to align the Perspectives 2 as documented in the 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan with the activities of the HRM Division as it presently stands. Perspective 2 speaks to: Employment Engagement; Competency-based Development; Culture of Employee Engagement and the Strengthening of Performance Systems. In an effort to properly gage the progress of each "Perspective", an evaluation tool in the form of review questions is documented in the Strategic Plan. The findings of this paper will therefore be closely measured against the documented review questions found in the Strategic Plan.

A. Research Question 1

Research Question - "Is the Human Resources Division at the University of the West Indies – St. Augustine strategic in nature"?

When examined it was discovered that the Human Resources Management Division located on the St. Augustine campus did not document a HR Strategy to match the 2007 – 2012 Strategic Plan neither was one documented for the 2012 – 2017 Strategic Plan up to the time of this Research paper.

The absence of formally documented competencies was also observed along with the fact that many positions listed on the organisation chart were absence of Job Descriptions and in cases where Job Descriptions existed they were out-dated.

The Division boast an elaborate Human Resources Information System (HRIS) equipped with the capability to generate extremely useful analytical data. However, it was observed that the system was grossly underutilized as the HR Metric document being produced were mainly administrative in nature and in no way strategically focussed.

The University of the West Indies –St. Augustine has a large workforce of Baby Boomers who are next in line (some have already began) to retire. With this fact in hand the HRM Division – St. Augustine should have well documented Succession Plans to cater to "this staff movement" in an organised and strategic fashion. Unfortunately, there is no Succession Plan in place.

It was also observed that the management style of Managers (Departmental Head included) and Senior Staff personnel were far from acceptable as many were technically competent but lack good managerial and people skills.

While the findings noted above can be categories as poor strategic practices, the Researcher has observed the following attempts to address some existing deficiencies namely:

- the development and introduction of a Talent Development Program for the ATS staff, (introduced in 2009, during the period of the 2007 – 2012 Strategic Plan) which will serve to assist in preparing the ATS Staff for promotional opportunities, while enhancing their competency base;
- the commencement of a Leadership and Management Training program aim at assisting the managerial staff to become more strategic and better leaders;
- an increase in the cadre of training courses, with areas such as Occupational Health and Safety awareness and practice being introduced.

The Researcher was told that the Division is presently embarking on a Competency-based documentation drive to uniformly document competencies to cover all job categories. It is hoped that a Job Description/Occupational Standard documentation program will also result from this exercise.

- It is also interesting to note that no evidence of High Performance Work System (HPWS) concept or practice was evident in the documentations reviewed.

B. Research Question 2

Research Question – "Will the strategic plan of the University of the West Indies be negatively affected if the Human Resources Management Division – St. Augustine fails to strategically align itself to the organisation's strategic direction?"

At the end of the 2007 – 2012 Strategic Plan period the Vice Chancellor, Nigel Harris stated that the University had failed to achieve all the stated goals and objectives documented in the then strategic plan, he identified the absence of an operational work plan to accompany the plan (The University of the West Indies. 2011, "Report of the Vice Chancellor's Strategic Planning Retreat – The University office of Planning and Development") and the lack of financial resources to undertake several of the initiatives tabled as the key factors for the missed opportunity.

The Vice Chancellor statement may be expanded to include the fact that the success of an organisation's Strategic Plan is heavily dependent on the HR Strategy development in answer to the Strategic Plan, as HRS are one category of operational work plans, and that with the absence of a HRS in 2007 -2012 the partial fulfilment of the Strategic Plan is of no surprise.

In an effort to become more strategic in 2012- 2017, the University conducted an Employee Engagement Survey with the hope of using the information garnered from the exercise to assist the organisation in meeting the needs of its employees through engagement initiatives.

C. Research Question 3

"Is the organisational culture negatively affecting the practice of positive Human Resource Management principles and practice?"

The University is unique because all four campuses are geographically diverse and are "govern" by different national, geographical and cultural needs, norms and beliefs, despite the fact that they all "fall" within the mandate of the University Strategic Plan and are required to "conform" to the rules thereof. In addition to which the UWI is also required to balance its central authority (Vice Chancellor) with its local authority (individual campus) in administering and managing the University's affairs. Despite this the paper will continue to focus on the St. Augustine campus.

The findings garnered from the Employee Engagement Survey conducted, listed the following areas as needing improvement:

- Communication
- Line of sight
 - Measuring people and holding them accountable for work they deliver
- Pride in organisation
 - Senior leadership acting inconsistent with organisation's stated values
 - Senior leadership needs to walk the talk
- Performance Management

- Implementation of systems and procedures to track and inform staff of progress in achieving their goals

The survey continues to note the following factors which also depict a case of “negative” organisational culture that could serve to impact the practice of HRM on the St. Augustine campus:

- A “very loose culture”
- “Power dynamics is at play”
- “lack accountability, ethical practice, trust and respect”

XIII. DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is hoped that when completed the HRS will speak to all relevant aspects of the current Strategic Plan while taking into considerations the resources of the HRM Division as well as that of the organisation. It therefore means that capacity building requirement of the HRM Division will need to be addressed if the organisation is to meet its strategic objectives. The HRS should therefore be built on the concept of a High Performance Work System (HPWS) which [29] define as “a specific combination of HR practices, work structures, and processes that maximizes employee knowledge, skill, commitment and flexibility” and which seeks to create an environment that encourages a higher level of staff involvement and will therefore be helpful in assisting the organisation in meeting its mandate. In an effort to ensure feedback and accountability a Balance Scorecard (BSC) system should also be included in the HRS as it focuses on the following four important elements found in an organisation’s strategic plan: learning and growth; business processes; customer and financial perspective. Since Organisational culture is an important factor influencing HR Strategic Management functions and it exerts a strong influence on both organisational and HR strategies, it too should not be taken lightly by the HRM Division during the documentation of the HRS, as it has the potential to negatively impact organisational goals and objectives if not properly addressed. The HRM Division should also ensure that the feedback from the Employee Engagement Survey is captured in the HRS document. The documentation of policies and procedures will be required to “regulate” the “initiatives” that will be included in the HRS.

In addition to the documentation of a Human Resource Strategy the HRM Division at the University of the West Indies – St. Augustine Campus needs to ensure that the competency exercise that will be undertaken is a comprehensive one and results in the documentation of either Job Descriptions or Occupational Standard documents for each positions on the organisational chart. The implementation of an organisation wide Job Evaluation exercise is also advice. In the same breathe the HRM Division needs to ensure that the criteria for the much needed

reviewed Performance Management exercise are linked to the organisational strategic goals and objectives, as this too will serve to assist in the success of the objectives. In should be noted that a comprehensive training program for the employees who will be conducting Performance Management Appraisals is critical.

As stated earlier in the paper a Succession Plan is needed as the organisation is poised to lose a significant portion of its workforce due to age, and without a well-documented and operational Succession Plan, the goals and objectives might be at risk because of a lack of manpower.

The organisation has already invested heavily into a state-of-the-art HRIS that has the capability to produce strategic data, but the system is presently highly underutilized because the Division does not have the required trained personnel to “operate” it. It is therefore being recommended that the Division invest in either training someone to undertake the task or recruiting someone who already has the requisite skill set. The HRM Division had also launched a Talent Acquisition Development and Mobility program for the ATS Staff, the recommendation is being made to extent the program to all categories and therefore make it a campus wide initiative, thereby allowing more people to benefit as the organisation increases its training opportunities.

It has been acknowledged that the University is unique in its campus locations and cultural differences that arise from same. In an effort to reduce the feeling of differences that may be present it is being recommended that a University wide Diversity Management training exercise be undertaken.

In [14], [16] and [25] definitions all agree that an organizational culture can negatively affect the practice of positive Human Resource Management principles and practice. This therefore means that the negative cultural currently being practice at the UWI – St. Augustine as noted in the Employee Engagement survey that was recently conducted has the potential to “derail” any positive initiatives documented in the HRS and could also aid in the failure of the organisation to meet its goals and objectives. In an effort to positively address the cultural abnormality the HRM Division may wish to implement the following recommendations: respond positively to the finding of the Employee Engagement Survey; introduce a mandatory campus-wide Diversity Management and Ethics Management Training program; Review the communication policy and practices; introduce Ethics Management Training for all Academic and Administrative level staff; have the HRM Division practice social responsibility and Business Partnering.

The poor ethical practices that is being perpetrated by the Management team if left unattended could result in unrealized organisational goals and objectives, as staff who are recipient of same may either withdraw or withhold their services. Since communication is the basic on which all relationships is built. Poor communication can serve to erect faulty structures made out of distrust, lack of respect, depression and thereby produce unhappy employees with no engagement attachment and motivation to ensure the success of the organisation’s goals. If

the recommended actions fail, the Researcher suggest that a Change Management option be investigated.

XIV. CONCLUSION

A successful Strategic Plan is the ideal for any organisation as it serves to confirm the good health of an organisation. To achieve it however, all members of staff have to be positively on-board and the Human Resources Management Department needs to be the driver. This however does not appear to be the situation as the University of the West Indies- St. Augustine as the HRM Division appears to be somewhat divorce from the proceedings.

It could be argued that the situation exist because of many reasons, some of which may be the reporting relationship of the HR Director, the non-strategic position of the HRM Division or the "loose, unethical and disrespectful culture on the campus or a combination of all factors or maybe none of the above. Despite which option is chosen the fact still remain that the Human Resources Management Division at the St. Augustine Campus of the University of the West Indies is not Strategic in nature, or better yet said...they are not there yet? However, it is felt that due to its positioning in the Region and its mandate it is critical that the Division becomes Strategic if it intends to take its rightful position as a member of the Senior Management team and therefore a Strategic player at the University of the West Indies.

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